

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Definition of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) = globally unique, actionable and machine-resolvable strings of (alpha) numeric characters that:

- act as a long-lasting reference to a digital object
- resolve to a central landing page
- are maintained by trustworthy organizations

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): example of syntax

Examples of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Full name	Acronym	PID for	Registration	Resolver
Digital Object Identifier	DOI 	Digital objects	Through a DOI Registration Agency such as DataCite	https://dx.doi.org/
Open Researcher Contributor Identification Initiative	ORCID 	Scientists	Self-registration	https://orcid.org/
Research Organization Registry	ROR ID 	Research institutions	On request via form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdJYaMTCwS7muuTa-B_CnAtCSkKzt19lkirAKG4u7umH9Nosg/viewform	https://fairsharing.org/4503
Research Activity Identifier	RAiD 	Research projects	API or manual minting?	https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.dc702a

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